

INFILTRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF *EUTRIC GLEYICFLUVISOL* UNDER COCOA PLANTATION

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ABSTRACT

Infiltration rate, cumulative infiltration and hydraulic conductivity of *Eutric gleyic fluvisols* soil subgroup under the cocoa plantation were investigated over 1950-ha Nkari subcatchment in Enyong creek catchment in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Infiltration rate and hydraulic conductivity were measured with double-ring infiltrometer and augur-hole method respectively. Data were processed for descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS software version 17(WORD). Word and predictive regression models were obtained. A constant infiltration rate of 5.2 cm/hr. (13.248 m/day) was obtained for its poorly drained clay soil subgroup, which was higher than typical value of its texture; hence, indicating the influence of soil bioturbation by cocoa roots, other soil ecosystem engineers, and vegetal surface layering on regulating the water balance under cocoa plantation. Empirical predictive models for infiltration rate and cumulative infiltration capacity were formulated, and conformed significantly and perfectly to Kostiakov model ($R^2 = 0.901$, $P < 0.1$). The soil drainage characteristics showed adequacy to sustain cocoa tree growth with little or no flood submergence. The cumulative infiltration equation followed the pattern of Philips infiltration model. Periodic re-evaluation every decade is recommended to link water balance in plantation soil with the age of cocoa plantation.

KEYWORDS: Cocoa plantation, *Eutric gleyic fluvisol*, infiltration rate, Kostiakov model, soil drainage properties.

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INTRODUCTION

Infiltration rate which characterizes the surface soil varies with the soil texture and cover, being greatly influenced by the depth and type of vegetative cover over the soil surface which dampen the kinetic energy impact of large raindrops against dislodging surface soil particles, and producing surface sealing and crusting. These factors affect surface drainage flow. In forested lands and plantations, infiltration along with water storage capacity and drainage, are affected by the interception of storey trees canopies, the litter layers on forest floors, and the bioturbation influence of soil ecosystem engineers (such as roots, earthworms, termites, ants and other macro-fauna) (Moreira et al 2008).

The hydrological dynamics in forest plantations are known to change after plantation establishment (Goldberg and Bemhofer 2001). A tropical secondary forest (as represented by cocoa plantation) may affect the climate, soil and hydrology differently from primary forests or agricultural areas (Godsey and Elsenbeer 2002). Comparison of three land uses – the primary forest, a former banana-mixed cocoa plantation and re-growth at an abandoned pasture – showed that the forest type or vegetation produced significant difference in lateral subsurface flow (drainage) response to intense rainfall in soil under them with respect to soil depth (Godsey and Elsenbeer 2002). The infiltration rate in forested area was observed to vary with understory vegetation and foliar

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coverage. For instance, the basal area of regrowth affected water yield (Godsey and Elsenbeer 2002). The vegetation influences the distribution of rainfall, which is the source of infiltration water (Vanclay 2009) although researches are sparse on this area. Most plantation establishments actively modify the soil to reduce runoff and improve infiltration (Evans and Turnbull 2004); but these effects are age-dependent water use trend occurring under vegetation, however publications on these effects are not many (Zimmermann et al. 2006). Thus, surface intake by infiltration rate and subsurface drainage by hydraulic conductivity are affected by the forested vegetation type.

Cocoa tree, a drought sensitive crop, can only withstand water-logging for a short period, although it needs constant rain (1500 – 2000mm) (RMRDC 2004). Therefore, soils under cocoa plantations must retain adequate moisture but offer good drainage properties, because cocoa plant with deep tap root system requires deep and well drained soils (Okpeke 2005), which are contingent on high infiltration rate and saturated hydraulic conductivity (Oguike and Henshaw 2013). Hence, both the soil infiltration and hydraulic conductivity are implicated in soil sustenance of productive cocoa plantation. The unavailability of such information, as in this case, makes it necessary to investigate the physical properties and hydrological characteristics of the supporting soil under the cocoa plantation.

Also spatial variability of surface soil properties and litter layers on forest floor can be major factors determining the infiltration rate (Hiraoka and Onda 2010); however, no infiltration rate relationship with these properties are sufficiently documented for the plantation soil. Therefore, specific field or basin-scale determination of infiltration rate under the plantation condition and age are needed. In the cocoa plantation at Nkari in Enyong Creek catchment, Nigeria, the infiltration characteristics and its relationship with soil properties were yet to be studied and documented for the 4-5 years cocoa plants in the plantation and the varied soil series of the sub catchment area. Therefore, the objectives of the research were: 1) to investigate the infiltration rate, cumulative infiltration and characteristics of the supporting soil under young cocoa plantation, both for baseline information and management to sustain the plantation under no flood condition; and 2) to establish the empirical predictive models for infiltration rate and cumulative infiltration capacity of the soil under cocoa plantation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Nkari Swamp Description

Field trips were undertaken to identify cocoa plantations and test sites locations. Nkari Swamp is located in the north-eastern border of Enyong Creek wetland in northern Akwa Ibom State, and lies within longitude $7^{\circ} 39^1 E - 7^{\circ} 50^1 E$, and latitudes $5^{\circ} 03^1 N - 5^{\circ} 27N$ in the present Ini Local Government Area, with a swamp area of 1950 ha as part of Itu River swamp (3170 ha) (Plate 1). It has a 1.5km wide flood plain bordering the Itu tributary River with several large swamp arms extending into the dissected river terraces. The swamp profile is generally flat with slopes less than 1% but with gentle undulations of river terrace up to 2m forming small islands of dry land. The area falls within 1:50,000 scale map sheet Ikot Ekpene 322 NW.

Soils

The predominant soils are the poorly drained clays of series EN 51 in central and eastern areas and EN 52 in western and north central parts. The imperfectly drained clays of series EN 31 and medium textured soils of EN 32 occur mainly as narrow strips along the edges of the uplands and as levee soils along the Itu River. A few small patches of the poorly drained medium textured series EN 53 and EN 54 occur in the eastern half of the swamp.

Vegetation and Land Use

The dominant vegetation and land use pattern is a mixed forest and cocoa plantation which occupy the northern side along the Itu River spanning about 50% of the swamp. The cocoa plantation is in most cases not continuous pure stands as it contains oil palms and various trees and woody shrubs. The swamp grasses and rice farms occupy the lower flood plains.

The soil sub group EN 51 in the cocoa plantation

Soil series or groups are groups of soils having the same parent materials, and development by the same pedological processes so that they have similar profile characteristics. The universal parent material in the swamp soils is riverine Alluvium which is divided into different types according to its texture and the nature of textural changes with depth (Akamigbo 1983; AKADEP 1995). The material is predominantly clay marked by minor amounts of sand and rare occurrence of gravel as contaminant. Therefore, the soil series are distinguished according to the soil texture, and down-the-profile texture sequence and by soil wetness indicated by the degree of gleying. The textural groups are the broad groups of coarse, medium and fine with subgroups comprising of clay and silty clay, as primary group, and sandy clay and gravelly clay as second group. The degree of gleying combines the intensity of the gleying and the depth at which it occurs (Akamigbo 1983; AKADEP 1995). The EN 51 soil group is the poorly drained clays classification or *eutric gleyic fluvisol* (USDA 1975; FAO 1985). It covers about 50% of the wetland soils in Enyong catchment. The topsoil varies between 10cm and 20cm in thickness and their textures ranges includes from sandy clay loam, silty clay and even silt loam. The colour varies from dark yellowish brown to grayish brown and dark reddish brown. The mottling ranges from none to strong brown mottles. The structure is commonly moderately and weakly developed medium subangular blocky, and sometimes is strongly developed coarse blocky (AKADEP 1995).

Plate 1: Map of Enyong Creek Catchment showing Nkari study site

Infiltration, hydraulic conductivity, and particle size measurement

The infiltration rates of soil surface under the cover of cocoa plantation were measured in January and February 2010 when any high water levels in the swamp edges or levees and even in the flood plain had been lowered. Infiltration rates were measured by double ring method (Bhattacharya and Michael 2003). The cocoa plantation covered varied toposequence and soil series as observed in Nkari study area. In addition to EN 51 soil group, cocoa plantations were distributed to imperfectly drained clays (EN 31 series) and to medium textured soils existing as narrow strips along the edges of the uplands and as levee soils along the Itu River. Therefore, at least one infiltration measurement was made at each of these locations, to obtain different infiltration rate

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measurements. Due to transport limitation, pre-wetting was prevented. The saturated hydraulic conductivity, K_{sat} , of the soil profile that supports the soil surface infiltration characteristics was also investigated by field measurement using standard in-situ single-auger hole method at the grid centres along the transects across the plantation.

The particle size was determined by hydrometer method (Liu and Evett 2000) for particles at specific grid points along cut-out transects in the cocoa plantations. Then the USDA soil classification triangle was used to find the texture.

Statistical analysis

Data and regression models were statistically analyzed using SPSS software version 17 (Words). Infiltration charts were plotted with computer. Regression equations were compared to Kostiakov and Philips infiltration models. Correlations between the observed and predicted models were extracted.

RESULTS

Field data were used to plot the graphs of infiltration rate and cumulative infiltration [infiltration capacity] with time under cocoa plantation. The curves for infiltration rate, I (cm/hr) on secondary axis and cumulative infiltration, F (cm) for *eutric gleyic fluvisol*, the poorly drained clays, are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Plot of measured cumulative infiltration and infiltration rate with time for Cocoa plantation soil (*Eutric gleyic fluvisol*)

Table 1 shows the infiltration rates for different soil characteristics of the soil subgroup EN 51 and silt/clay ratios for two depths of cocoa plantation floor at Nkari wetland.

Table 1: Soil group, particles sizes, silt/clay ratio, infiltration rates, permeability of soil under cocoa plantation, Nkari

Soil group property	Depth, cm	
	0 – 19	19 – 39
EN 51	Poorly drained clays	
pH	4.77	4.69
Sand %	32.6	21.6
Silt %	32.0	22.0
Clay %	35.4	56.4
Silt/Clay ratio	0.904	0.390
SOM	2.87	1.02
Texture	CL	C
Infiltration rate, cm/hr (m/day)	55.2 (0.552)	
	Ksat, m/day	6.8

N/B: 50m = soil organic matter; Ksat – saturated hydraulic conductivity, CL = Clay loam; C = Clay *. The soil is a texture contrast duplex

Table 2: Monthly and annual rainfall in the cocoa plantation catchment (1972 – 1999)

Months	Mean Rainfall, mm
Jan	10.7
Feb	30.7
Mar	131.9
Apr	188.0
May	252.2
Jun	275.4
Jul	292.3
Aug	304.9
Sep	339.5
Oct	224.9
Nov	54.6
Dec	10.7
Total	2113.9

DISCUSSION

Physical soil properties

The supporting soil is required to contain significant percentage of sand in some areas and high proportions of silt and clay dominating in other areas (Ololade et al 2010). Table 1 shows that the cocoa plantation soil, the *Eutric gleyic fluvisol*, of the alluvial deposits contains significantly high percentage of silt and clay with high proportion of sand. It is adequate for sustained growth of cocoa (Ololade et al 2010; Fashina et al 2007). Rainfall is required to constantly maintain the soil, as the crop is drought or heat sensitive (RMRDC 2004; CTA 2012). The distribution of rainfall (Table 2) shows adequacy.

November, December, January, February and March (i.e. 5 months) in the catchment are the months when irrigation, especially sprinklers or the drip type, may be supplied. However, because of the forest-like nature of the cocoa plantation (Oguike and Henshaw 2013), which intercept solar radiation and reduce soil temperature, mitigation of the negative warming effects of the climate change (as in dry season) may be expected. This is one aspect that more research is needed to avert restricted production (Oguike and Henshaw 2013; CTA 2012). Using the soil particle size, structure and drainage class, soil erodibility of the sub-catchment was obtained (Ogban et al. 1999; Essien 2013) and was found to be low perhaps, in this case, due to low silt, clay and generally low fines content also. Also, the soil erodibility under the surface layer of plantation litters could be reduced by increasing surface soil resistance through crop residue mulching which protects against raindrop impact; and the decomposition provides organic matter which binds soil particles into a stable aggregate and fertile soil (Lal 1983).

Infiltration rate and cumulative capacity

From the graphical plot (Fig. 1), the constant infiltration rate was obtained as 0.92 cm/min or 60.5cm/hr or 60×10^{-2} m/hr. The cumulative infiltration capacity, from Fig. 1, was read as 61.9cm in 1hr or 95cm in 1½ hrs constant infiltrating. The equation for model infiltration rate from the curve in Fig. 1 was obtained as a power function given as:

$$I = 90.073t^{-0.1133}, R^2 = 9056. \tag{1}$$

where I = infiltration rate, cm/hr., and t is time, min, elapsed since infiltration started. Also, the cumulative infiltration capacity, from Fig.1, was obtained as a linear function given by:

$$F = 0.9916t + 2.2536, R^2 = 0.9951 \tag{2}$$

Comparative Models

Two forms of model were compared to the empirical regression equations obtained above. These were the earliest infiltration model or Kostiakov’s (1932) model given as:

$$f = at^b \tag{3}$$

where f is infiltration rate in time (mm/hr) and t is time since infiltration started (hrs), a and b are soil parameters depending on antecedent soil water content and soil structural stability (Orebode and Yahaya 2008).

Patenting the empirical equation for the cocoa plantation infiltration rate in the form of Kostiakov model gave the Kostiakov form of the cocoa plantation infiltration rate equation as a power function given by:

$$I = 90.073 t^{-0.1133} \tag{4}$$

Thus, Kostiakov parameter a = 90.073, and b (soil dependent parameter) = 0.1133. The second model form was the Philip’s (1957) two-term quadratic equation for cumulative infiltration given as:

$$F = St^{1/2} + Ct \tag{5}$$

Equation 2, the cumulative infiltration equation for the cocoa plantation soil, could be made to conform with this model (Equation 5) by taking similar terms between the decomposed components of the Philips equation, Equation 5, and the decomposed components of the empirical cumulative infiltration capacity of the cocoa plantation soil, Equation 2. Thus;

$$St^{1/2} = 0.9916t = S \Rightarrow 0.9916 t^{1/2} \tag{6}$$

$$Ct = 2.2536 = C \Rightarrow 2.2536t^{-1} \tag{7}$$

Substituting t into these partial functions showed the variation of S and C with elapsed time. In the alternative, therefore, Equation 5 is equated to empirical Equation 2. Thus;

$$F = St^{1/2} + Ct = 0.9916t + 2.2536 \quad (8)$$

By inserting the values of t and F into Equation 8, a series of equation with S and C as unknown variables are obtained, which can be solved simultaneously using determinant matrix to obtain minimum values of silt and clay with relatively high percentage of sand. It is therefore adequate for cocoa plantation.

Basic infiltration rate

The empirical constant infiltration rate for the cocoa plantation’s *Eutric gleyic fluvisol* soil, obtained from field measurement was 0.92 cm/min or 55.2cm/hr while the model basic form, using the Kostiakov model, was 54 cm/hr or 54×10^{-2} m/hr. The difference between the empirical (field data based) infiltration rate and the Kostiakov model form (as observed in Fig. 2) was not significant (at $P < 0.01$; $r = 0.995$). Thus, the Kostiakov model was efficient predictive function of the cocoa plantation infiltration rate under *eutric gleyic fluvisol* soil subgroup.

Fig.2: Comparison of measured and predicted (Kostiakov’s model) infiltration rate

Fig.3: Comparison of measured and predicted (Philip’s model)cumulative infiltration

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Prediction of cumulative infiltration capacity on the *Eutric gleyic fluvisol* soil type also conformed to the two-term Philip's equation. The difference between the field data-based cumulative infiltration function was not significantly different from the profile obtained from Philip's equation as seen in Fig. 3. Already the dominant soil group (EN 51) was *Eutric gleyic fluvisol* – which is gleyed poorly drained wetland soil. It is not necessary to encourage flooding on such a gleyed land. As such, infiltration rate should be aligned for proper soil and water management of the plantation. Thus, irrigation by flooding is not recommended.

CONCLUSION

Investigation of the soil under cocoa plantation showed that the soil group, *Eutric gleyic fluvisol* supported the sustenance of cocoa plantation with good soil drainage properties. The infiltration rate, cumulative infiltration and saturated hydraulic conductivity of the soil were determined, and data processed, using SPSS software version 17. The constant infiltration rate was 55.2 cm/hr and was efficiently correlated with the Kostiakov infiltration model with $R^2 = 0.901$, and no significant difference ($P < 0.01$) between the empirical and Kostiakov models. The model parameters were in consonance with the Kostiakov coefficients. However, the high value of infiltration rate under the cocoa plantation was indicative of the bioturbation and growth influence of plantation and soil ecosystem engineers. With low erodibility class, the high infiltration rate incapacitated high flood level submergence of plantation.

Infiltration re-evaluation at 10 year's interval is needed to re-assess goodness of fit of predictive model with empirical infiltration equation for all soil groups under the canopy, for efficient water balance and management of cocoa plantation on basins wetland.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author confirms that to the best of his knowledge, no conflict of interest exists.

REFERENCES

- Akamigbo FOR, Asadu CLA (1983) Influence of parent materials on the soils of South Eastern Nigeria. *East African Agric. For J.*, 48, 81 – 91.
- Akwa Ibom Agricultural Project (AKADEP) (1995) AKADEP, Uyo Northern Akwa Ibom Swamp Development Study, Stage 2 Report. 5, 1 – 12.
- Bhattacharya AK, Michael AM (2003) Land Drainage Principles, Methods and Application, Konark Publishers Pvt. Ltd. Delho.
- CTA (2012) Warmer climate kills trees: concerns for cocoa. *Spore*, 159, 69. s
- Essien OE (2013) Evaluation of potential soil erodibility of basins wetland from soil particle size distribution. *IORS JAVS*. 4(4): 10 – 16.
- Evans J, Turnbull J (2004) Plantation Forestry in the Tropics, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1-467.
- FAO – UNESCO (1985) Revised Legend World Soil Resources Report 60. Soil map of the world, FAO of UN, Rome.
- Fashina AS, Omotosho SO, Shitu OS, Adenikinju AP (2007) Properties, evaluation and suitability evaluation of some selected cocoa soils of South Western Nigeria. *American – Eurasian J. Agric and Environ Science* 2(3), 312 – 317.

Godsey S., Elsenbeer H. (2002) The hydrologic response to forest regrowth: a case study from South Western Amazon. *Hydrol. Process*, 16 (7), 1519 – 1522. Doi: 10.1002/hyp. 605.

Goldberg V, Bemhofer C (2001) *Ann. Geophys*, 19, 581 – 587.

Hiraoka M, Onda Y (2010) Factors affecting infiltration rate in steep hillslope conifer plantation American Geographical Union: Code 2010 AGUFMH31F1065.

Lal R (1983) Soil erosion control in humid tropics with particular references to agricultural land development and management. In Proc. Hamburg Symp. IAHS Publ No. 140: 221 – 239.

Liu C, Evett JB (2000) Grain-Size Analysis of Soil, ASTM D 422, Prentice Hall, New Jersey. Washington D. C.

Moreira FM, Huising EJ, Bignell DE (2008) Handbook of Tropical Soil Biology, Earthscan, London.

Oguike PC, Henshaw IE (2013) Evaluation of water retaining and conducting characteristics, aggregates stability and bulk density of cocoa growing soils in Ikwano Abia State Nigeria *Int'l Journal of Agric and Rural Development*, 16 (1), 1343 – 1347.

Ogban PI, Ekerete IO, Effiong GS, Onofiok OE (1999) Soil characteristics and management of erosion problems in South eastern Nigeria. In Rethinking efficiency, effectiveness, equity and sustainability of irrigation development (Nwa EU, Adeniji FA, Abubarkar SS, Jimoh RA (eds)). Proc. Int. Seminar, Abuja, Nigeria. NINCID/ICID, Abuja, pp 276 – 294.

Okpeke LK (2005) Tropical Tree Crops. Spectrum books Ltd. Ibadan, Nigeria.

Ololade IA, Ayaji IR, Gbadamosi AE, Mohammed OZ, Sunday AG (2010) A study on effects of soil physico-chemical properties on cocoa production in Ondo State. *Modern Applied Sciences* 4 (5), 35 – 43.

Oyebode MA, Yahaya AS (2008) Evaluation of two infiltration of some models' parameters on irrigation experimental plot. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Technology*, 16 (2), 44-52.

RMRDC (2004) Report on Survey of Agro Raw Materials in Nigerian. Cocoa, Maiden edn. Raw Material Research and Development Council, Abuja, Nigeria.

Soil Survey Staff (1975) Soil Taxonomy. Agric Handbook No. 436. USDA.

Vanclay JK (2009) Managing water use from forest plantations. *Forest Ecology and Management* 257 (2), 385 – 389.

Zimmermann B, Elsenbeer H, De Moraes JM (2000) Influence of land-use changes on soil hydraulic properties: Implication for runoff generation. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 222, 29-38.
